

Effects of Land Use Types and Soil Depth on Selected Soil Physicochemical Properties at Danka Watershed in Dinsho District of Bale Highland, Southeastern Ethiopia

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Abstract

Land use type and soil depth significantly affect soil physicochemical properties, influencing soil fertility and sustainability. This study assessed the effects of land use and soil depth on selected soil properties in the Danka Watershed. Soil samples were systematically collected from natural forest, grazing, and cultivated lands at depths of 0–20, 20–40, and 40–60 cm in three replications. Soil laboratory analysis were conducted using standard laboratory procedures, and statistical analyses were conducted in R software to determine significant variations across land use types and soil depths. The results indicated that land use type had a significant effect ($p \leq 0.05$) on the soil's physical and chemical properties. Results showed significant differences among land use types ($p < 0.05$). Natural forest soils had the highest silt (31.44%) and clay (46.15%) content, giving a clay texture, while cultivated soils had the highest sand content (31.67%). Field capacity (FC) and permanent wilting point (PWP) were greatest in natural forest (43.89% and 36.56%) and lowest in cultivated land (29.29% and 25.24%). Available water holding capacity (AWHC) was significantly reduced in cultivated soils (4.05%) compared to natural forest (7.33%) and grazing land (7.26%). Natural forest also showed the highest soil pH (5.82), organic matter (4.38%), and total nitrogen (0.3893%), while cultivated land had the lowest pH (5.26), OM (1.83%), TN (0.1252%). Available phosphorus (13.65 mg/kg) and cation exchange capacity (36.31 cmol(+)/kg) were highest in natural forest and lowest in cultivated land (3.05 mg/kg and 18.46 cmol(+)/kg). Overall, natural forest soils were of highest quality, followed by grazing land, while cultivated soils were most degraded mainly due to continuous cropping, erosion, low phosphorus input, and organic matter loss highlighting the need for sustainable soil fertility restoration. It is recommended to implement sustainable land management practices such as forest conservation, conservation agriculture, and integrated soil fertility and watershed management to restore and sustain soil health.

Keywords: Cultivated land; Forest land; Grazing land; Physicochemical.

Introduction

Land use is a complex and dynamic process influenced by an interplay of natural factors and human activities (Senait *et al.*, 2019). Understanding the relationship between land use and soil properties is essential because changes in soil quality can lead to decreased crop yields, increased vulnerability to erosion, and diminished capacity to support biodiversity. This linkage becomes especially crucial in the context of global challenges like food security and climate resilience. Globally, land degradation driven primarily by inappropriate land use and unsustainable practices has emerged as one of the most pressing environmental issues of the twenty-first century (Ebabu *et al.*, 2017 and Terefe *et al.*, 2020).

Direct causes of land use and land cover (LULC) change include unsustainable land management practices, insecure land tenure systems, and suboptimal farming techniques, while poverty indirectly exacerbates land degradation by limiting access to sustainable land management options. Anthropogenic drivers such as population growth, evolving socioeconomic conditions, agricultural expansion, policy shifts, and environmental stressors have significantly shaped land use patterns worldwide (Nguyen *et al.*, 2024). Land use encompasses the deliberate choices, actions, and allocation

of resources by individuals and communities to develop, modify, or maintain specific land cover types (Ufot *et al.*, 2016 and Tigist *et al.*, 2023).

The alteration of land cover through various land use practices profoundly influences soil physical and chemical properties such as texture, structure, nutrient availability, and moisture retention which are critical determinants of agricultural productivity and overall ecosystem health. It undermines efforts toward environmental conservation and sustainable development by reducing soil fertility, disrupting water cycles, and threatening the livelihoods of millions dependent on agriculture. The pervasive issue of land degradation continues to hinder agricultural productivity and environmental sustainability, posing significant obstacles to socioeconomic development (Berhanu *et al.*, 2016 and Ademe *et al.*, 2017).

The Danka watershed in the Dinsho District of the Bale Highlands is experiencing increasing pressure from expanding agricultural activities, overgrazing, and deforestation. These changes in land use have significantly altered the natural balance of the soil ecosystem. As a result, the physical and chemical properties of the soil such as structure, texture, bulk density, organic matter content, nutrient availability, and pH are being degraded, leading to reduced soil fertility, increased erosion, and declining agricultural productivity.

Despite ongoing challenges, there is a critical lack of site-specific data on how varying land use types natural forest, grazing land, and cultivated land affect key soil physical and chemical properties in the Danka watershed. This gap in knowledge hinders the development of targeted soil and water conservation strategies that align with the area's unique ecological and socio-economic conditions. Without concrete evidence on the influence of land use on soil health, the long-term sustainability of the watershed's agricultural productivity and natural resources is at serious risk.

Baseline information on the effects of different land use types on soil physicochemical properties is critically needed to inform decision-making, enhance sustainable land management practices, and support the development of effective policies in the Danka watershed. Therefore, this study aimed to assess the effects of land use and soil depth on selected soil properties in the Danka Watershed.

Materials and Methods

Description of the Study Area

The research was conducted in the Danka watershed, located in the Bale Highlands of southeastern Ethiopia, approximately 400 km southeast of Addis Ababa and 30 km from Robe, the administrative center of the Bale Zone in the Oromia Regional State. Geographically, the Danka watershed lies between 6°56'0" and 7°6'0" N latitude and 39°44'30" and 39°52'30" E longitude. The watershed spans an area of 7,084 hectares, with an elevation ranging from 3,066 to 4,139 meters above sea level (masl) (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Study area Danka Watershed map, contour lines, elevation, and sampling points.

Climate conditions

The study area is characterized by a mid-subtropical highland climate with two distinct agricultural seasons locally known as Ganna (March to June) and Bona (December to July). Rainfall is distributed over an extended eight-month period from late March to October, ranging between 600–1000 mm in lower altitude areas and 1000–1400 mm in higher elevations. The temperature fluctuates between a minimum of 2°C and a maximum of 20°C, supporting a diverse agricultural system. The topography and altitude vary significantly, influencing both land use and production systems.

Farming system

The area's economy is primarily driven by agriculture, with mixed farming serving as the predominant system. This approach integrates both livestock rearing including cattle, sheep, and horses and crop production. Farming is largely rainfed, with barley as the dominant crop, followed by wheat, while vegetables such as cabbage and potatoes are also commonly grown, contributing to household food security and income diversification.

Soil sampling and preparation

The Danka watershed was stratified into three replications to ensure comprehensive soil data collection, with samples taken from key land use types: natural forest, grazing land, and cultivated land. Employing a random sampling approach, soil was collected at three depths (0–20 cm, 20–40 cm, and 40–60 cm) to capture vertical variability, resulting in 54 composite samples. Each sample was labeled, air-dried, ground using a mortar and pestle, and sieved through a 2 mm mesh for most analyses and a 0.5 mm mesh for organic carbon and total nitrogen determinations. All physicochemical analyses were performed following standard procedures at the Haramaya University Soil Laboratory, Melkasa Agricultural Research Center, and Sinana Agricultural Research Center.

Soil Laboratory Analysis

Soil physical and chemical properties were analyzed using standard procedures. Particle size distribution was measured by the hydrometer method (Bouyoucos, 1962), and textural classes were identified using the USDA textural triangle. Bulk density (BD) and particle density (PD), were determined following Blake and Hartge (1986a) and Blake and Hartge (1986b), respectively, Barauah and Barthakur (1997) to determine Field capacity (FC) and permanent wilting point (PWP) were assessed at -33 kPa and -1500 kPa using a pressure membrane apparatus, enabling calculation of available water holding capacity. Soil chemical properties, soil pH was measured in a 1:2.5 soil-to-water ratio using a digital pH meter. Organic carbon (OC) was analyzed using the Walkley and Black method (1934), and organic matter (OM) was calculated as $OC \times 1.724$. Total nitrogen (TN) was determined via the Micro-Kjeldahl method (Bremner and Mulvaney, 1982), available phosphorus (Av.P) using the Olsen method (Olsen et al., 1954), and cation exchange capacity (CEC) through ammonium acetate leaching (Chapman, 1965). These analyses offered key insights into soil fertility and productivity potential.

Statistical Analysis

Statistical analyses were performed using R 4.1.1 to assess mean separation among land use types and soil depths. Differences were evaluated using LSD at a 5% significance level.

Result and Discussions

Effects of land use and soil depth on selected soil physical properties

Soil color varied across land uses, reflecting differences in organic matter content and management. Natural forest soil had the darkest moist color (7.5YR 2.5/1; black), due to high organic matter from litter accumulation and minimal disturbance. When dry, it turned dark brown (10YR 3/3) (Table 1).

Grazing land showed a lighter moist color (7.5YR 3/2; brown) and dried to the same dark brown (10YR 3/3), indicating moderate organic content. Cultivated land had the lightest moist color (7.5YR 3/2; brown), drying to 10YR 4/4 (dark yellowish brown), suggesting low organic matter from tillage, residue removal, and erosion (Table 1). This aligns with findings by Dinku *et al* (2014), Lawal (2014), and Usmael *et al* (2018), who also reported darker soils in forest lands and variations in soil color due to land use differences.

Table 1. Soil color characteristics of Danka watershed

Land use types	Description at Moist		Description at dry	
Natural Forest land	7.5YR 2.5/1	black	10YR 3/3	dark brown
Grazing Land	7.5YR 3/2	brown	10YR 3/3	dark brown
Cultivated Land	7.5YR 3/2	brown	10YR 4/4	dark yellowish brown

Soil Particle size distribution

The results showed that soil particle size distribution was significantly affected by land use types. Cultivated land had the highest sand content (31.67%), significantly greater than that of grazing (24.85%) and natural forest land (22.41%) ($P = 0.00$), likely due to long-term cultivation and erosion removing finer particles (Table 2). The result aligns with the findings of Daniel (2020), Belayneh and Eyasu (2020), and Tigist *et al* (2023), who reported that degraded lands are often initially dominated by sand particles due to the selective removal of finer particles through erosion.

In contrast, natural forest and grazing lands had significantly higher silt contents (31.44% and 31.26%, respectively) compared to cultivated land (26.59%) ($P = 0.0263$), possibly due to better vegetation cover that minimizes erosion and preserves finer particles. Although clay content did not differ significantly across land use types ($P = 0.2585$), natural forest land had the highest clay percentage (46.15%) (Table 2). Consistent with this finding, Ufot *et al* (2016); Eyayu and Mamo *et al* (2018) and Tigist *et al* (2023) reported the highest clay content under natural forest land, likely due to dense vegetation cover minimizing soil erosion and thereby preventing clay depletion.

Soil particle distribution varied significantly with depth. Sand content decreased from 28.19% at 0–20 cm to 22.93% at 40–60 cm ($P = 0.0049$), likely due to finer particles moving downward and sand accumulating in the topsoil (Table 2). Silt content also declined sharply with depth, from 36.44% to 24.93% ($P = 0.0000$), reflecting surface enrichment from organic matter and limited soil disturbance. In contrast, clay content increased significantly with depth, rising from 35.37% in the topsoil to 52.15% in the subsoil ($P = 0.0000$), indicating clay illuviation (Table 2).

Texture classes varied by land use and soil depth: natural forest land was clay; grazing and cultivated lands were clay loam. Soil texture changed with depth from loam (0–20 cm) to clay loam (20–40 cm) and clay (40–60 cm). Higher clay content in deeper layers and natural forest reflects less disturbance and soil development, while surface layers and cultivated/grazing lands show more balanced textures due to erosion and management practices.

Table 2. Effects of land use types and soil depth on soil particle size distribution of Danka watershed

Factors	Sand (%)	Silt (%)	Clay (%)	Texture Classes
Land use types				
Natural forest land	22.41 ^b	31.44 ^a	46.15	Clay
Grazing Land	24.85 ^b	31.26 ^a	43.89	Clay Loam
Cultivated Land	31.67 ^a	26.59 ^b	41.74	Clay Loam
Mean	26.31	29.77	43.93	
CV (%)	4.99	4.56	3.21	
LSD (0.05)	2.9936	3.9625	NS	
P(value)	0.00	0.0263	0.2585	
Soil depth (cm)				
0 – 20	28.19 ^a	36.44 ^a	35.37 ^c	Loam
20 – 40	27.81 ^a	27.93 ^b	44.26 ^b	Clay Loam
40 – 60	22.93 ^b	24.93 ^b	52.15 ^a	Clay
Mean	26.31	29.77	43.93	
CV (%)	4.26	3.43	5.87	
LSD (0.05)	3.4597	3.1344	3.7791	
P(value)	0.0049	0.0000	0.0000	

Where; Means followed by similar lower case letter (s) indicate across columns and rows are not significantly different ($p = 0.05$) with respect to land use types, and soil depths.

Soil Bulk Density, Particle Density and Total porosity

The soil bulk density showed a significant difference among land use types ($P = 0.0000$), with the lowest value observed in natural forest (1.22 g/cm^3), followed by grazing land (1.38 g/cm^3), and the highest in cultivated land (1.54 g/cm^3) (Table 3). The lower bulk density in the forested area indicates well-aggregated and loose soil structure, likely due to high organic matter input and minimal soil disturbance. In line with the findings of Bizuhoraho et al (2018), the lowest bulk density in forest land is attributed to minimal soil disturbance, higher organic matter from litter input, better aggregation, and enhanced root growth with lower resistance. In contrast, the higher bulk density in cultivated land suggests soil compaction resulting from repeated plowing and the use of heavy machinery. This result aligns with findings by Bizuhoraho et al (2018), Belayneh and Eyasu (2020), Daniel (2020), Dereje (2020), and Tigist et al (2023), attributing higher bulk density in cultivated land to low organic matter, frequent soil disturbance, and compaction.

The results showed that soil particle density significantly differed ($P = 0.0001$) with land use types, increasing from forest soils (2.50 g/cm^3) to cultivated lands (2.60 g/cm^3) (Table 3). This rise likely reflects differences in mineral composition, where cultivated soils contain more heavy mineral particles and less organic matter, resulting in a higher average particle density. Total porosity varied significantly across land use types ($P = 0.0000$), with the highest value recorded in natural forest land (51.36%), followed by grazing land (46.02%), and the lowest in cultivated land (40.99%) (Table 3). The greater porosity in forest soils is likely due to higher organic matter content and active root systems that enhance soil structure. Conversely, repeated tillage and soil compaction in cultivated areas reduce pore space and limit soil aeration. This finding agrees with studies by Kedir and Henok (2020), Eyayu and Mamo (2018), and Tigist et al (2023), who reported higher total porosity in forest land and lower in cultivated land.

Soil bulk density (BD) and particle density (PD) significantly increased with depth ($p < 0.05$), while total porosity (TP) showed a decreasing trend but was not statistically significant ($p > 0.05$). The highest BD (1.46 g/cm^3) and PD (2.61 g/cm^3) were recorded at 40–60 cm, indicating compaction and reduced porosity with depth (Table 3). Similarly, the increase in soil bulk density with depth may be due to greater compaction, reduced root penetration, and lower organic matter in subsurface layers, as reported by Bizuhoraho *et al* (2018), and Tigist *et al* (2023). These variations reflect natural soil compaction and organic matter decline in deeper layers, influencing water movement, root growth, and soil aeration. The decrease in total porosity with soil depth is likely due to the weight of overlying soil and declining organic matter, consistent with findings by Eyayu and Mamo (2018) and Tigist *et al* (2023).

Table 3. Effects of land use types and soil depth on total porosity, Bulk and particle density

Factors	TP (%)	BD (gcm^{-3})	PD (gcm^{-3})
Land use types			
Natural forest land	51.36 ^a	1.22 ^c	2.50 ^c
Grazing Land	46.02 ^b	1.38 ^b	2.55 ^b
Cultivated Land	40.99 ^c	1.54 ^a	2.60 ^a
Mean	46.12	1.38	2.55
CV (%)	8.11	9.62	3.02
LSD (0.05)	2.0269	0.0719	0.0417
P(value)	0.0000	0.000	0.0001
Soil depth (cm)			
0 – 20	47.93	1.30 ^b	2.49 ^c
20 – 40	46.11	1.38 ^{ab}	2.56 ^b
40 – 60	44.33	1.46 ^a	2.61 ^a
Mean	46.12	1.38	2.55
CV (%)	6.03	5.87	2.83
LSD (0.05)	NS	0.0962	0.0392
P(value)	0.0643	0.0084	0.0000

Where; Means followed by similar lower case letter (s) indicate across columns and rows are not significantly different ($p = 0.05$) with respect to land use types, and soil depths.

Soil water characteristics

The result revealed that field capacity (FC), was significantly different with land use types in which the highest in natural forest land (43.89%), followed by grazing land (37.70%), and lowest in cultivated land (29.29%) ($P = 0.0000$) (Table 4). This might be due the higher FC under forest is due to better soil structure, organic matter, and porosity, which enhance water retention. In contrast, cultivated land has degraded structure and reduced organic matter, leading to poor water-holding ability.

Similarly, PWP was significantly different with land use types in which it was highest under natural forest (36.56%), moderate in grazing (30.43%), and lowest in cultivated land (25.24%) ($P = 0.0000$) (Table 4). This might be due to soils with higher clay and organic matter content, like forest soils, tend to hold more water even at wilting point while cultivated land, being more compacted and sandy, retain less water.

The results indicated that Available Water Holding Capacity (AWHC) was significantly greater under natural forest (7.33%) and grazing land (7.26%), compared to cultivated land (4.05%) ($P = 0.0000$) (Table 4). Thus means forest and grazing lands maintain higher differences due to better structure and organic content, while cultivate land reduces this difference through compaction and organic matter loss.

Although FC, PWP, and AWHC values increased slightly with depth, from 0–20 cm to 40–60 cm, differences were not statistically significant ($P > 0.05$). As the results indicated varied from 33.51% (0–20 cm) to 40.25% (40–60 cm), 27.82% to 33.65% and 5.69% to 6.60% FC, PWP and AWHC, respectively (Table 4). This the slight increase with depth may be due to greater clay content in lower layers, which enhances water retention. However, the variation was not large enough to be statistically significant, possibly due to uniform texture or small sample variation.

Table 4. Effects of land use types and soil depth on soil water characteristics at Danka Watershed

Factors	FC (%)	PWP (%)	AWHC (%)
Land use types			
Natural forest land	43.89 ^a	36.56 ^a	7.33 ^a
Grazing Land	37.70 ^b	30.43 ^b	7.26 ^a
Cultivated Land	29.29 ^c	25.24 ^c	4.05 ^b
Mean	36.96	30.74	6.21
CV (%)	4.36	4.73	8.04
LSD (0.05)	4.4797	4.1215	0.9445
P(value)	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000
Soil depth (cm)			
0 – 20	33.51	27.82	5.69
20 – 40	37.11	30.76	6.35
40 – 60	40.25	33.65	6.60
Mean	36.96	30.74	6.21
CV (%)	6.84	8.09	7.32
LSD (0.05)	NS	NS	NS
P(value)	0.0500	0.0519	0.3397

Where; Means followed by similar lower case letter (s) indicate across columns and rows are not significantly different ($p = 0.05$) with respect to land use types, and soil depths.

Effects of land use and soil depth on selected soil chemical properties

Soil pH

The pH result was significantly different with land use types, accordingly, highest in natural forest land (5.82), followed by grazing land (5.49) and lowest in cultivated land (5.26) ($P = 0.0000$) (Table 5). This implies forest soils maintain more neutral pH due to higher organic matter and biological activity, which buffer soil acidity. This result aligns with the findings of previous studies conducted by Weldemariam *et al* (2020) and Tigist *et al* (2023), indicating consistency and reinforcing the reliability of the current outcome. In contrast to this cultivated land often becomes more acidic over time due to continuous use of acid-forming fertilizers, leaching, and reduced organic input. In contrast, however, studies by Nahusenay and Kibebew (2016) reported the lowest soil pH values under natural forest land, suggesting site-specific differences or variations in soil-forming factors and management history. Soil pH increased significantly with depth 5.41 (0 – 20 cm), 5.49 (20 – 40 cm), and 5.67 (40 – 60 cm) ($P = 0.0045$) (Table 5). The lower pH in surface soils may result from organic acid production, leaching of base cations, and fertilizer use, while subsoils, less affected by these factors, show relatively higher pH.

Soil Organic Matter

Soil organic matter (OM %) was highly significant with land use types, accordingly it was highest under natural forest (4.38%), followed by grazing land (3.08%), and lowest in cultivated land (1.83%) ($P = 0.0000$) (Table 5). This means undisturbed forest ecosystems accumulate organic matter from leaf litter and root turnover. This finding is consistent with the results reported by Assefa *et al* (2020), Olorunfemi *et al* (2018), Tumayro and Tesgaye (2021), and Tigist *et al* (2023), who observed higher organic matter content in soils under natural forest compared to the lowest levels found in cultivated lands. Grazing land maintains moderate organic matter (OM) levels due to continuous grass cover. In contrast, cultivated land experiences reduced OM as a result of frequent tillage, removal of crop residues, and increased soil erosion. This finding is consistent with the studies conducted by Assefa *et al* (2020) and Tigist *et al* (2023), who reported the lowest organic matter content under cultivated land. This decline was attributed to continuous cultivation, which accelerates the oxidation of organic carbon and increases carbon dioxide emissions.

Soil organic matter (OM %) content declined significantly with increasing soil depth, following the trend: 4.12% at 0–20 cm > 2.96% at 20–40 cm > 2.20% at 40–60 cm ($P = 0.0000$) (Table 5). This is because organic inputs, such as plant residues and litter fall, are concentrated at the soil surface, while biological activity decreases with depth, leading to reduced organic matter accumulation in the subsoil. This finding is also in agreement with studies conducted by Assefa *et al* (2020), Belayneh and Eyasu (2020), and Tigist *et al* (2023), who reported a gradual decrease in organic matter content with increasing soil depth. This downward trend may be attributed to the higher accumulation and decomposition of plant litter at the surface, resulting in reduced organic matter availability in deeper soil layers.

Total nitrogen (TN)

Total Nitrogen (TN %) followed the same trend organic matter, natural forest land (0.3893%) > grazing land (0.2593%) > cultivated land (0.1252%) ($P = 0.0000$) (Table 5). This because forest soils, rich in organic inputs, support higher nitrogen levels, while cultivated soils are depleted due to removal of biomass and low residue return. Similarly, higher total nitrogen in forest and grazing lands has been reported, likely due to greater organic matter content an important nitrogen source through mineralization and favorable forest microclimates that reduce nitrogen loss via volatilization (Tumayro and Tesgaye, 2021; Weldemariam, 2020; and Tigist *et al.*, 2023). In contrast, the lowest total nitrogen in cultivated land may be due to continuous cultivation, which depletes organic matter, promotes surface runoff, and enhances nitrate leaching. Similar findings were reported by Bizuhoraho *et al* (2018), Jemal and Tesfaye (2020), and Tigist *et al* (2023). Thus, total nitrogen content in soils of Danka watershed follows the order: natural forest land > grazing land > cultivated land.

Total Nitrogen (TN %) decreased significantly with soil depth, following the order: 0.3359% (0–20 cm) > 0.2452% (20–40 cm) > 0.1926% (40–60 cm) ($P = 0.0032$) (Table 5). This is because nitrogen, like organic matter, is concentrated in the topsoil due to the accumulation of surface organic inputs and higher microbial activity, whereas the lower organic matter content in deeper layers results in reduced nitrogen retention. This finding is also consistent with studies by Eyayu and Mamo (2018), Desta (2018), and Tigist *et al* (2023), who reported a decline in total nitrogen with soil depth, likely due to reduced inputs of nitrogen-rich materials such as plant biomass, manure, and other organic debris in deeper layers.

Table 5. Effects of land use types and soil depth on selected soil chemical properties for soils of Danka Watershed

Factors	pH-H ₂ O	OM (%)	TN (%)
Land use types			
Natural forest land	5.82 ^a	4.38 ^a	0.3893 ^a
Grazing Land	5.49 ^b	3.08 ^b	0.2593 ^b
Cultivated Land	5.26 ^c	1.83 ^c	0.1252 ^c
Mean	5.52	3.10	0.2579
CV (%)	3.70	3.05	6.20
LSD (0.05)	0.1107	0.5043	0.0646
P(value)	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000
Soil depth (cm)			
0 – 20	5.41 ^b	4.12 ^a	0.3359 ^a
20 – 40	5.49 ^b	2.96 ^b	0.2452 ^b
40 – 60	5.67 ^a	2.20 ^c	0.1926 ^b
Mean	5.52	3.10	0.2579
CV (%)	5.31	7.53	8.61
LSD (0.05)	0.1590	0.6298	0.0819
P(value)	0.0045	0.0000	0.0032

Available phosphorus

The results indicated that soil available phosphorus (Av.P), accordingly, the highest Av.P was recorded under natural forest land (13.65 mg/kg), followed by grazing land (10.64 mg/kg), and the lowest under cultivated land (3.05 mg/kg) ($P = 0.0000$) (Table 6). This means the forest soils retain more phosphorus due to high organic matter and minimal disturbance, which improve P availability while the grazing land maintains moderate levels through manure inputs. In contrast, cultivated lands often suffer P depletion due to continuous crop uptake, erosion, and limited organic inputs. This result contradicts the findings of Mengistu *et al* (2017) and Bizuhoraho *et al* (2018), who reported that the highest available phosphorus levels were observed on cultivated land, likely due to the continuous application of phosphorus-rich fertilizers such as diammonium phosphate (DAP) and the regular addition of manure.

The soil available Phosphorus (Av.P) was decreased significantly with depth: 12.26 mg/kg (0–20 cm) > 8.39 (20–40 cm) > 6.68 (40–60 cm) ($P = 0.0006$) (Table 6). This means phosphorus is immobile and largely accumulates in surface soil due to fertilizer application, organic matter decomposition, and limited leaching, in contrast subsoil layers receive minimal input, resulting in lower P levels. This result aligns with the findings of Tigist *et al* (2023), who reported a downward decrease in available soil phosphorus, likely due to the higher clay content in the subsurface soil layers, which enhances phosphorus fixation. This suggests that increased clay content in the soil can significantly reduce the availability of phosphorus by converting it into forms that are not accessible to plants.

Cation exchange capacity

Cation Exchange Capacity (CEC) followed a similar trend natural forest (36.31 cmol(+)/kg) > grazing land (25.38) > cultivated land (18.46) ($P = 0.0000$) (Table 6). The reason for the high CEC in forest soils is attributed to richer organic matter and higher clay content, both of which contribute exchange sites. Similarly, the highest CEC level observed in natural forest land may be attributed to its high organic matter and clay content, both of which possess negatively charged sites that can retain and exchange cations. This observation is consistent with the findings of Olorunfemi *et al* (2018), and Tigist *et al* (2023).

In contrast the cultivated land, depleted of organic matter and subject to erosion, has reduced nutrient-holding capacity. This is consistent with the findings of Mengistu *et al* (2017), Tumayro *et al* (2021), and Tigist *et al* (2023), who reported the lowest CEC levels under cultivated land, likely due to the depletion of organic matter caused by continuous and intensive cultivation practices. The results of cation exchange capacity (CEC) also declined significantly with soil depth follows in the orders of 31.52 (0–20 cm) > 25.97 (20–40 cm) > 22.65 (40–60 cm) ($P = 0.0077$) (Table 6). This decrease is linked to the reduction in organic matter and biological activity with depth. The surface horizon, rich in humus and fine particles, offers higher CEC, whereas subsoil layers are more mineral and less reactive.

Table 6. Effects of land use types and soil depth on available phosphorus and cation exchange capacity for soils of Danka Watershed

Factors	Av.P (mg/kg)	CEC cmol(+)/kg
Land use types		
Natural forest land	13.65 ^a	36.31 ^a
Grazing Land	10.64 ^b	25.38 ^b
Cultivated Land	3.05 ^c	18.46 ^c
Mean	9.11	26.72
CV (%)	7.04	9.27
LSD (0.05)	1.8292	4.2384
P(value)	0.0000	0.0000
Soil depth (cm)		
0 – 20	12.26 ^a	31.52 ^a
20 – 40	8.39 ^b	25.97 ^b
40 – 60	6.68 ^b	22.65 ^b
Mean	9.11	26.72
CV (%)	6.81	8.25
LSD (0.05)	2.8054	5.5397
P(value)	0.0006	0.0077

Conclusion and Recommendation

Conclusion

This study confirms that both land use and soil depth significantly affect soil physical and chemical properties in the Danka watershed. Natural forest soils had the best quality due to minimal disturbance and continuous litter input, while cultivated soils were degraded by erosion, tillage, and poor residue management. Surface layers (0–20 cm) were more fertile and moister, while deeper layers (40–60 cm) were denser and nutrient-poor.

Overall, soil quality ranked as: Natural Forest > Grazing Land > Cultivated Land and Topsoil > Subsoil, emphasizing the need for sustainable land use and vegetation conservation. These findings underscore the vital importance of sustainable land management practices, natural vegetation conservation, and the adoption of conservation agriculture and Integrated Soil Fertility Management (ISFM) approaches to restore and maintain soil health in cultivated lands within the watershed.

Recommendation

It is strongly recommended to preserve existing natural forests to maintain soil fertility, quality, and watershed functionality, and preventing their conversion is crucial for halting further soil degradation.

It is recommended to adopt conservation agriculture and integrated soil fertility management (ISFM) practices through crop rotation, the use of cover crops, application of organic amendments, and reduced tillage to rehabilitate degraded croplands and improve soil health.

Targeted integrated watershed management is recommended to reduce runoff and prevent topsoil loss on sloped agricultural and grazing lands by using measures like terracing, contour plowing, and vegetation barriers.

It is recommended to implement rotational grazing systems and focus fertility inputs in the topsoil layer (0–20 cm), while also addressing nutrient deficiencies and compaction problems in the subsoil (20–60 cm).

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Conflict of interest

The authors declared there is no conflict of interest in this research.

References

- Ademe, Y., Kebede, T., Mullatu, A., & Shafi, T. (2017). Evaluation of the effectiveness of soil and water conservation practices on improving selected soil properties in Wonago district, Southern Ethiopia. *Journal of Soil Science and Environmental Management*, 8(3), 70–79. <https://doi.org/10.5897/JSSEM2017.0620>
- Assefa, W. W., Eneyew, B. G., & Wondie, A. (2021). The impacts of land-use and land-cover change on wetland ecosystem service values in peri-urban and urban area of Bahir Dar City, Upper Blue Nile Basin, Northwestern Ethiopia. *Ecological Processes*, 10(1), 39. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s13717-021-00311-2>
- Baruah, T. C., & Barthakur, H. P. (1997). *A textbook of soil analysis*. Vikas Publishing House.
- Belayneh, B., & Elias, E. (2020). Effects of land use/land cover changes on selected soil physical and chemical properties in Shenkolla watershed, south central Ethiopia. *Advances in Agriculture*, 2020(1), 5145483. <https://doi.org/10.1155/2020/5145483>
- Birhanu, L., Hailu, B. T., Bekele, T., & Demissew, S. (2019). Land use/land cover change along elevation and slope gradient in highlands of Ethiopia. *Remote Sensing Applications: Society and Environment*, 16, 100260. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rsase.2019.100260>
- Bizuhoraho, T., Kayiranga, A., Manirakiza, N., & Mourad, K. A. (2018). The effect of land use systems on soil properties: A case study from Rwanda. *Sustainability in Environment*, 3(1), 49–69. <https://doi.org/10.22158/se.v3n1p49>
- Blake, G. R., & Hartge, K. H. (1986a). Bulk density. In A. Klute (Ed.), *Methods of soil analysis: Part 1. Physical and mineralogical methods* (2nd ed., pp. 363–375). ASA and SSSA.
- Blake, G. R., & Hartge, K. H. (1986b). Particle density. In A. Klute (Ed.), *Methods of soil analysis: Part 1. Physical and mineralogical methods* (2nd ed., pp. 377–382). ASA and SSSA.
- Bouyoucos, G. J. (1962). Hydrometer method improved for making particle size analyses of soils. *Agronomy Journal*, 54(5), 464–465. <https://doi.org/10.2134/agronj1962.00021962005400050028x>
- Bremner, J. M., & Mulvaney, C. S. (1982). Nitrogen total. In A. L. Page (Ed.), *Methods of soil analysis: Part 2. Chemical and microbiological properties* (2nd ed., pp. 595–624). ASA and SSSA.

11. Chapman, H. D. (1965). Cation exchange capacity. In C. A. Black (Ed.), *Methods of soil analysis: Part 2. Chemical and microbiological properties* (pp. 891–901). ASA and SSSA.
12. Negasa, D. J. (2020). Effects of land use types on selected soil properties in central highlands of Ethiopia. *Applied and Environmental Soil Science*, 2020(1), 7026929. <https://doi.org/10.1155/2020/7026929>
13. Girma, D. (2020). Effect of land use types on selected soil physical and chemical properties at Sire Morose sub watershed, central highland of Ethiopia. *International Journal of Engineering Research and Technology*, 9(5), 770–779.
14. Desta, H. A. (2018). Effects of land use systems on soil fertility at Antra watershed, Chilga district, northwestern highlands of Ethiopia. *Universal Journal of Agricultural Research*, 6(6), 194–208. <https://doi.org/10.13189/ujar.2018.060601>
15. Dessalegn, D., Beyene, S., Ram, N., Walley, F., & Gala, T. S. (2014). Effects of topography and land use on soil characteristics along the toposequence of Ele watershed in southern Ethiopia. *Catena*, 115, 47–54. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.catena.2013.11.007>
16. Fetene, E. M., & Amera, M. Y. (2018). The effects of land use types and soil depth on soil properties of Agedit watershed, Northwest Ethiopia. *Ethiopian Journal of Science and Technology*, 11(1), 39–56.
17. Jemal, K., & Tesfaye, H. (2020). Soil physico-chemical property characterisation along different land use systems in Gurage Zone, Southern Ethiopia. *Modern Chemistry*, 8(3), 40–47.
18. Lawal, B. A., Tsado, P. A., Eze, P. C., Idefoh, K. K., Zaki, A. A., & Kolawole, S. (2014). Effect of slope positions on some properties of soils under a *Tectona grandis* plantation in Minna, Southern Guinea Savanna of Nigeria. *International Journal of Research in Agriculture and Forestry*, 1(1), 37–43.
19. Chemed, M., Kibret, K., & Fite, T. (2017). Influence of different land use types and soil depths on selected soil properties related to soil fertility in Warandhab area, Horo Guduru Wallaga Zone, Oromia, Ethiopia. *International Journal of Environmental Sciences and Natural Resources*, 4(2), 555634. <https://doi.org/10.19080/IJESNR.2017.04.555634>
20. Abate, N., & Kibret, K. (2016). Effects of land use, soil depth and topography on soil physicochemical properties along the toposequence at the Wadla Delanta Massif, Northcentral Highlands of Ethiopia. *Environment and Pollution*, 5(2), 57–71. <https://doi.org/10.5539/ep.v5n2p57>
21. Olorunfemi, I. E., Fasinmirin, J. T., & Akinola, F. F. (2018). Soil physico-chemical properties and fertility status of long-term land use and cover changes: A case study in forest vegetative zone of Nigeria. *Eurasian Journal of Soil Science*, 7(2), 133–150. <https://doi.org/10.18393/ejss.329238>
22. Olsen, S. R. (1954). *Estimation of available phosphorus in soils by extraction with sodium bicarbonate* (USDA Circular No. 939). US Department of Agriculture.
23. Terefe, H., Argaw, M., Tamene, L., Mekonnen, K., Recha, J., & Solomon, D. (2020). Effects of sustainable land management interventions on selected soil properties in Geda watershed, central highlands of Ethiopia. *Ecological Processes*, 9(1), 14. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s13717-020-00218-8>
24. Asmare, T. K., Abayneh, B., Yigzaw, M., & Birhan, T. A. (2023). The effect of land use type on selected soil physicochemical properties in Shihatig watershed, Dabat district, Northwest Ethiopia. *Heliyon*, 9(5), e16211. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.heliyon.2023.e16211>
25. Tumayro, M., & Tesgaye, D. (2021). Impact of land use types and soil depths on selected soil physicochemical properties in Fasha District, Konso Zone, Southern Ethiopia. *Journal of Soil Science and Environmental Management*, 12(1), 10–16. <https://doi.org/10.5897/JSSEM2020.0830>
26. Ufot, U. O., Iren, O. B., & Njoku, C. U. C. (2016). Effects of land use on soil physical and chemical properties in Akokwa area of Imo State, Nigeria. *International Journal of Life Sciences Scientific Research*, 2(3), 273–278.
27. Mohammed, U., Kibret, K., Mohammed, M., & Diriba, A. (2018). Soil fertility assessment and mapping of Becheke Sub-Watershed in Haramaya District of East Hararge Zone of Oromia Region, Ethiopia. *Journal of Natural Sciences Research*, 8(20), 37–49.
28. Walkley, A., & Black, I. A. (1934). An examination of the Degtjareff method for determining soil organic matter, and a proposed modification of the chromic acid titration method. *Soil Science*, 37(1), 29–38. <https://doi.org/10.1097/00010694-193401000-00003>
29. Seifu, W., Elias, E., & Gebresamuel, G. (2020). The effects of land use and landscape position on soil physicochemical properties in a semiarid watershed, northern Ethiopia. *Applied and Environmental Soil Science*, 2020(1), 8816248. <https://doi.org/10.1155/2020/8816248>